

Review Article

Reversed Phase HPLC Methods for the Analysis of Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs: A Comprehensive Review

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Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are the group most often used in human and veterinary medicine, since they are available without prescription for the treatment of fever and minor pain. The clinical and pharmaceutical analysis of these drugs requires effective analytical procedures for quality control, as well as pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic studies. An extensive survey of the literature published in various analytical and pharmaceutical chemistry-related journals has been conducted regarding the instrumental analytical methods developed and used for the determination of various NSAIDs. Analytical method development and its validation is an important aspect of the drug discovery process. Reverse Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) is the most common analytical method utilized for the analysis of drugs due to its accuracy, selectivity, and sensitivity. The development and validation of analytical methods provide accurate and precise data to ensure drug quality and safety. Several methods of analysis are reported and available for the estimation of NSAIDs, including RP-HPLC. This review article briefly discusses the analytical methods available for the estimation of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, specifically focusing on RP-HPLC.

Keywords: Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, RP-HPLC, Method development, Analytical techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Overview of Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs

Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) are a diverse group of compounds with similar biological capabilities: all NSAIDs reduce or eliminate the erythema, swelling, elevated temperature and pain caused by a variety of inflammatory stimuli. The mechanisms of action of NSAIDs have not yet been fully elucidated, but evidence suggests that their anti-inflammatory effects are primarily achieved through inhibiting prostaglandin production. This mode of action is common to all NSAIDs [1]. The cyclooxygenase enzyme was first identified as the therapeutic target of NSAIDs by Vane in 1971, showing that these anti-inflammatory substances block the biosynthesis of prostaglandins (PGs) that contribute to a variety of

physiological and pathophysiological functions [2]. The most prominent NSAIDs are aspirin, and naproxen, all available over the counter in most countries. Paracetamol (acetaminophen) is generally not considered an NSAID because it has only little anti-inflammatory activity. It treats pain mainly by blocking COX-2 mostly in the central nervous system, but not much in the rest of the body. Cyclooxygenase (COX) inhibitors, commonly called non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as ibuprofen, diclofenac, and naproxen, have anti-inflammatory and analgesic/antipyretic properties across a wide range of dosing regimens. Prescription-strength NSAIDs are effective for relief of chronic musculoskeletal pain and inflammation in conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis (RA) or osteoarthritis (OA) [3]. All NSAIDs inhibit COX, an enzyme that converts arachidonic acid to prostaglandins, thereby mediating pain,

inflammation, and fever. In the process, prostaglandin H₂ is converted to five primary prostaglandins, including thromboxane A₂ (which stimulates platelet aggregation and blood clot formation) in platelets and prostacyclin (a vasodilator that inhibits platelet aggregation) in the endothelium. Two COX isoenzymes (COX-1 and COX-2) are commonly recognized. In general, COX-1 is constitutively

expressed and is involved in gastroprotection from stomach acid and in thromboxane formation by platelets. COX-2 is inducible by inflammatory mediators in a wide range of tissues and has been associated with inflammation; however, it may also be constitutively expressed, where it contributes to renal physiology, reproductive function, bone resorption, and neurotransmission. [4]

Fig 1. Mechanism Action of Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs. [4]

Table No 1: Chemical classification of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents [5]

Class	Drugs
1. Salicylic acid derivatives	Acetyl salicylic acid (Aspirin), sodium salicylate, salicylamide
2. P-aminophenol derivatives	Paracetamol
3. 2-Aryl propionic acid derivatives	Ibuprofen, ketoprofen, naproxen
4. Enolic acid derivatives	Meloxicam, piroxicam, tenoxicam, lornoxicam.
5. Arylalkanoic acid derivatives	Indomethacin, Diclofenac, aceclofenac, etodolac, sulindac.
6. N-Arylanthranilic acids (fenamic acid)	Mefenamic acid, tolfenamic acid, meclofenamic acid
7. Selective COX-2 inhibitors	Celecoxib, rofecoxib, etoricoxib, parecoxib.
8. Sulphonilides	Nimesulide.
9. Benzoxazocine derivatives	Nefopam.

RP-HPLC Principle and Relevance in Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory Drug Analysis

Basic Principle of RP-HPLC

Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) is a widely used chromatographic technique that separates analytes

based on their hydrophobic interactions with a non-polar stationary phase and a polar mobile phase [6]. Typically, C₁₈ or C₈ silica-based columns are employed, where non-polar compounds exhibit longer retention times compared to polar compounds [7]. The flexibility of RP-HPLC allows modification of the mobile phase composition, pH, and flow rate to

achieve optimal separation, making it particularly suitable for multi-component drug formulations [8].

Comparison with Other Analytical Techniques

Although other analytical methods such as UV-spectrophotometry, spectrofluorimetry, and LC-MS/MS are used in pharmaceutical analysis, each has limitations compared to RP-HPLC. UV-spectrophotometry is simple and cost-effective but lacks specificity in multi-component analysis due to overlapping absorption spectra [9]. Spectrofluorimetry provides higher sensitivity than UV methods but is limited to fluorescent compounds and often requires derivatization steps [10]. LC-MS/MS, while highly sensitive and selective, involves higher costs, complex instrumentation, and extensive sample preparation, limiting its routine use in quality control [11]. In contrast, RP-HPLC provides the best balance of sensitivity, selectivity, reproducibility, and cost-effectiveness, making it the gold standard for estimation of NSAIDs.

Method Development Strategies

Selection of Stationary and Mobile Phases

The selection of appropriate stationary and mobile phases is critical for successful separation in RP-HPLC. Non-polar stationary phases such as octadecylsilane (C18) are most commonly used due to their ability to provide excellent resolution for a wide variety of drug molecules [9]. The mobile phase typically consists of a mixture of water (or buffer) and organic solvents such as methanol or acetonitrile, which are chosen based on analyte solubility and retention behavior [10]. Proper selection helps in achieving shorter run times and better peak symmetry [12].

pH and Buffer Optimization

pH plays a vital role in controlling the ionization state of analytes, which directly affects their retention time and resolution. For weakly acidic or basic drugs, selecting an optimal pH (usually between 2.5–7.5) ensures consistent ionization and sharp peaks [13]. Buffers such as phosphate or acetate are often used to maintain pH stability during analysis. Incorrect pH

can lead to peak tailing, poor reproducibility, and reduced column life [14].

Column Selection (C18, C8, etc.)

Column selection is crucial for resolving drugs with diverse physicochemical properties. C18 columns are the most widely used due to their high hydrophobic interactions and versatility [9]. However, shorter-chain columns such as C8 or phenyl columns may be preferable for highly hydrophobic drugs or when faster analysis is required [8]. Selection often depends on the complexity of the drug mixture and desired run time [15].

Gradient vs Isocratic Methods

RP-HPLC uses both isocratic and gradient elution techniques. Isocratic techniques are straightforward, repeatable, and appropriate for formulations including analytes with comparable polarity. However, for complicated drug combinations with large polarity differences, gradient methods which entail a gradual shift in the mobile phase's composition are beneficial because they speed up analysis and increase resolution. [16]

Analytical Challenges in Estimation of NSAIDs

The analytical estimation of Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) in pharmaceutical formulations and biological matrices presents several challenges due to their physicochemical properties and matrix-related interferences.

Chemical Diversity: NSAIDs exhibit wide structural diversity and varying pKa values, which complicates the development of a single analytical method suitable for all NSAIDs. Their acidic nature affects extraction efficiency and chromatographic behaviour.

Poor Aqueous Solubility: Many NSAIDs such as ibuprofen and diclofenac have low water solubility, leading to difficulties in dissolution, extraction, and reproducibility during analysis.

Matrix Interference: Pharmaceutical excipients may interfere with UV or chromatographic detection. Biological matrices (plasma, serum) contain proteins and endogenous compounds that can cause signal

suppression or overlapping peaks, necessitating complex sample preparation. [17]

Lack of Selectivity in UV Methods: Most NSAIDs absorb in the UV region (200–300 nm), resulting in overlapping spectra and poor selectivity, especially in multi-component formulations.

Stability Issues: NSAIDs are susceptible to hydrolysis, oxidation, and photodegradation, which can affect assay accuracy unless proper storage and analytical conditions are maintained.

Low Concentration Levels: In biological samples, NSAIDs are present at very low concentrations,

requiring highly sensitive analytical techniques such as HPLC or LC–MS/MS.

Chiral Nature: Some NSAIDs (e.g., ibuprofen, ketoprofen) are chiral, and enantiomers may differ in pharmacological activity, necessitating chiral separation techniques. Ensuring accuracy, precision, linearity, and robustness is challenging due to variability in formulations and biological matrices. [18]

Chromatographic Conditions for NSAIDS based on there classification:

1.Salicylic Acid Derivatives

Table No 2: chromatographic condition for salicylic acid derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Aspirin [19]	Tablet	Hypersil BDS C ₁₈ column (100×4.6 mm, 3µm)	Sodium perchlorate buffer (pH2.5): acetonitrile: isopropyl alcohol(85:14:1% v/v)	UV detection at 275 nm
Salicylamide [20]	Bulk API dosage form	C ₁₈ (250cm× 4.6 mm,5µm) column	Buffer: acetonitrile (40:60v/v). pH adjusting to 3.2	UV detection at 245 nm

2.P-aminophenol Derivatives

Table No 3: chromatographic condition for P-Aminophenol derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Paracetamol [21]	Tablet	Phenomenex C ₁₈ column (250 mm ×4.6 mm, 5µm)	Acetonitrile: water (60:40 v/v)	UV detection at 210 nm

3. 2-Arylpropionic Acid derivatives

Table No 4: chromatographic condition for 2-Arylpropionic acid derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Ibuprofen [22]	Tablet	Thermo hypersil BDS, C ₁₈ (150 ×4.6mm ,5µm)	Buffer (HPLC grade water: triethylamine: orthophosphoric acid 1000:1.0:0.5 ml)	UV detection at 220 nm
Ketoprofen [23]	Tablet	LiChrosorb C ₁₈ column (250mm×4.6mm, 5µm)	Methanol: 0.1 M ammonium acetate buffer pH 6.9: triethylamine: acetonitrile (73:20:5:2) (v/v/v/v)	UV detection at 230 nm
Naproxen [24]	Tablet	Phenomenex C ₁₈ column (250 mm ×4.6 mm, 5µm)	Dibasic Sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.80: Acetonitrile (70:30) (v/v)	UV detection at 225 nm

4. Enolic Acid Derivatives

Table No 5: chromatographic condition for Enolic acid derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Meloxicam [25]	Tablet	Micro Bandapak 125A C18 (10 μ) column	Methanol: water (70 :30 v/v)	UV detection at 230 nm
Piroxicam [26]	Tablet	SB-C ₁₈ Eclipse (150 mm \times 4.6mm,5 μ m)	Acetonitrile: Water (50:50) (v/v)	UV detection at 360 nm
Naproxen [27]	Blood plasma	Hypersil C18 column (10 cm \times 5mm,3 μ m)	ethanol: acetate buffer: acetonitrile (59:29:12 v/v/v)	UV detection at 328 nm
Lornoxicam [28]	Tablet	Eclipse C ₁₈ Column (150 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	Methanol:0.1% Fomic Acid in water (80:20 v/v)	UV detection at 381 nm

5. Arylalkanoic Acid Derivatives

Table No 6: chromatographic condition for Arylalkanoic acid derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Diclofenac sodium [29]	Bulk and Tablet formulation	Hypersil C18 column (250mm \times 4.6mm,5 μ m)	Acetonitrile: Phosphoric acid buffer pH7(50:50% v/v)	UV detection at 220 nm
Aceclofenac [30]	Tablet	Promesil C18 (250mm \times 4.6mm,5 μ m)	Water: acetonitrile (55:45 v/v)	UV detection at 277 nm
Etodolac [31]	Tablet	Phenomenex Luna C18(250 mm \times 4.6mm, 5 μ m)	Acetonitrile: Methanol (65:35 v/v)	UV detection at 226 nm
Sulindac [32]	Human serum	Hypersil C18 column (10 cm \times 5mm,3 μ m)	Methanol: acetate buffer: acetonitrile (59:29:12 v/v/v)	UV detection at 328 nm

6. N-Arylanthralinic acid derivatives (fenamic acid)

Table No 7: chromatographic condition for Arylalkanoic acid derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Mefenamic acid [33]	Bulk and Tablet formulation	Princeton SPHER-100 C ₈ (250mm \times 4.6mm,5 μ m)	Ammonium buffer: Acetonitrile: THF (55:45 v/v)	UV detection at 285 nm
Tolfenamic Acid [34]	Tablet	Promesil C ₁₈ (250mm \times 4.6mm,5 μ m)	Acetonitrile: water (90:10 v/v) at pH 2.5	UV detection at 280 nm

7. Selective COX-2 inhibitors

Table No 8: chromatographic condition for Selective COX-2 inhibitors

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Celecoxib [35]	Capsule dosage formulation	Develosil ODS HG (250×4 mm, 10µm)	acetonitrile:water (60:40 v/v)+1 ml Triethylamine+1 ml orthophosphoric acid	UV detection at 265 nm
Rofecoxib [36]	Tablet	Symmetry C ₁₈ (4.6 x 150 mm, 5µm)	Methanol and water (45:55 % v/v)	UV detection at 260 nm
Etoricoxib [37]	Tablet	Hypersil ODS C ₁₈ (250×4.6mm,5µm)	ACN: 0.05M KH ₂ PO ₄ (pH 4.2) (46:54% v/v)	UV detection at 280 nm

8. Sulphonilides derivative

Table No 9: chromatographic condition for Sulphonilides derivative

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Nimesulide [38]	Tablet	Avantor Ace 5 C ₁₈ 250mm×4.6mm, 4µm)	Acetonitrile: water: Triethylamine (50:49.5:0.5, v/v/v)	UV detection at 230 nm

9. Benzoxazocine Derivatives

Table No 10: chromatographic condition for Benzoxazocine Derivatives

Name of Drug	Sample Matrix	Chromatographic Condition	Mobile Phase	Detector
Nefopam [39]	Bulk and dosage formulation	Waters C ₁₈ (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	Hexane sulfonic acid buffer pH 2.7: Acetonitrile: Methanol (55:30:15 v/v/v)	UV detection at 215 nm

CONCLUSION

This review has summarized the development and validation of analytical methods for the estimation of Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) across various matrices, including pharmaceutical formulations, bulk substances, and biological samples. Through the application of RP-HPLC, both individual drugs and multi-component combinations can be analysed with high precision. Ongoing advances in method development specifically in mobile-phase design, judicious column selection, and optimized gradient elution have significantly reduced run times and improved resolution at disparate dose levels. These enhancements have bolstered the ruggedness, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness of NSAID analysis in routine quality control (QC) and bioanalytical settings. Looking ahead, research should prioritize eco-friendly and high-throughput strategies,

such as the adoption of green solvent systems, UHPLC miniaturization, and increased automation. Furthermore, greater hyphenation with Mass Spectrometry (MS) is essential to extend sensitivity and selectivity for complex biological matrices. Collectively, these advancements will consolidate the central role of RP-HPLC while aligning analytical practices with sustainability and next-generation clinical and regulatory requirements.

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